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Under the sign of the Blue Plague: human vulnerability in the context of cholera outbreaks in the nineteenth-century Porto

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Title: Under the sign of the Blue Plague: Human Vulnerability in the context of cholera outbreaks in the nineteenth-century Porto

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Abstract: This paper presents an ongoing research project dedicated to the study of human vulnerability associated with the cholera outbreaks that affected the city of Porto between 1832 and 1899. The project seeks to reconstruct the temporal and spatial patterns of mortality, analyse institutional and community responses, and identify the sociobiological determinants of vulnerability that shaped the experience of the epidemic. The study draws upon a wide range of historical sources and is linked to the *BeFRAIL – Porto in Times of Cholera and War: A Bioarchaeological Approach to Human Frailty* project (DOI: <https://doi.org/10.54499/2022.02398.PTDC>).

Keywords: Human vulnerability; Cholera; Mortality; Sociobiological determinants; Nineteenth-century Porto.